

Digital Throws of the Dice: A Genealogy of Rhetoric in *Fallout*

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In 1994, a developer at Interplay Entertainment began staying after hours working on their private pet project. Over the following three years, that project would become *Fallout: A Post Nuclear Role Playing Game* (Interplay Inc. 1997). *Fallout* would go on to spawn many more iterations, culminating in 2024 in a widely popular television series.

However, *Fallout's* humble origins can be traced back to an altogether different medium: tabletop role playing games (TTRPGs) (Tresca 2016). *Fallout's* developers played TTRPGs religiously and were determined to model their games after them. Out of the many contemporary TTRPG systems, *Fallout* drew most from the *Generic Universal RolePlaying System 3rd Edition (GURPS)* (Jackson, Koke, and Smith 2018; Campbell 2012; Cain 2023). For most of its development, *Fallout* was titled *Fallout: A GURPS Post-Nuclear Adventure* (Interplay Inc. 1996). However, Interplay would eventually drop the *GURPS* license during development, leading *Fallout's* developers to revise their role-playing system (Campbell 2012; Dransfield 2019; Cain 2012). This re-coded system would be the foundation of the modern screen-based role-playing game (RPG) as *Fallout* would go on to inspire and define entire genres. In tracing this history of table-top to computer screen, I offer a genealogy of play. My methodology intersects computational humanities, data-driven analysis, retrocomputing, and interface theory.

World Maps in *GURPS* and *Fallout*

"Caravan to Ein Arris"

Fallout

Figure 1: The maps of the worlds in the two mediums. On the left is a world map of a sample *GURPS* adventure "Caravan to Ein Arris". On the right is the interface of the world map of *Fallout* at an early stage of the game.

Role-playing systems consist of hundreds of pages of rules, but I want to focus on the specific game mechanics which regulate *rhetoric*: those interactions which entail persuasion, discourse, and lies. In order to theorize these mechanics and to trace specific genealogies from *GURPS* to *Fallout*, I employ the concept of "operationalization," borrowing Franco Moretti's definition of the practice as "building a bridge from concepts to measurement, and then to the world" (Moretti 2013). This theoretical framework can be employed at different contextual strata. First, I tie the concepts of implementations of rhetoric, progression through dialogue, and archetype to *Fallout* through

quantitative methods. Second, I interact with operationalization not as a methodology, but instead by conceptualizing game mechanics as diegetic operationalizations of fictive concepts.

I first engage with operationalization by applying computational methods to a dataset of *Fallout's* dialogue. In doing so, I seek to add to my theoretical conclusions by operationalizing concepts of dialogue structure, character interaction, and rhetoric to make “the leap from measurement to reconceptualization” (Moretti 2013). My dataset consists of directed graphs, with nodes representing possible actions or dialogue choices the player can make with a given non-player character (NPC) [Figure 2]. All NPCs, from the primary antagonist to a generic merchant, are included. I begin by identifying instances of reaction rolls and skill checks.

“Aradesh’s” Dialogue Tree

Figure 2: A Sample Dialogue Tree. Dialogue trees are used to represent conversations between the player and a non-playable character (NPC). In this case, a “player dialogue” node refers to a combination of player-chosen lines and the response of the NPC. Players navigate through the tree by choosing different dialogue options, which in turn open up new ones. In the case of *Fallout*, some dialogue options will only reveal themselves based on the current knowledge (or rhetorical skill) of the player-character.

Figure 3: Clustering on Dialogue Graph Embeddings

My operationalizing methods range from statistical analysis on the constructed graph attributes to unsupervised clustering of graph and node embeddings (Rozemberczki, Kiss, and Sarkar 2020; Narayanan et al. 2017) [Figure 3, Figure 4] and the application of LLMs for dialogue behavior detection (Finch, Paek, and Choi 2023). I use topic-extraction techniques to identify the contexts in which rhetoric is employed (Grootendorst 2022). While performing these methods, I reflexively

conceptualize the contact between modern computational practices and legacy software as a form of *retrocomputing* (Kirschenbaum 2015; Takhteyev and DuPont 2024).

Figure 4: Results of KMeans Clustering on Graph Embeddings. The number of KMeans clusters is set to 2; number of neighbors for UMAP projection is set to 7; graph embeddings have a dimensionality of 32.

Next, I step into the fiction of games and conceptualize “game mechanics” as *diegetic* operationalizations. There are two main mechanics of rhetoric which I can string between the mediums: the “reaction roll” and the “skill check.” Both mechanics convert concepts into quantified discretizations, and then extend the results of that measurement onto the narrative fiction of a game. A reaction roll operationalizes “first impressions:” what kind of opinion would a NPC have of a player given the player character’s past associations, physical appearance, and overall demeanor? A skill check operationalizes the application of a player character’s abilities to a specific task: e.g. lockpicking a door, finding their way after getting lost, or lying to a guard. Instead of relating concepts to theory *around* a text, diegetic operationalization acts *within* the text.

Given the lack of a dataset of rhetoric in *GURPS* games, a deconstructionist approach forms the foundation of my analysis of the two operationalizations of rhetoric. As discussed by Olivier Caïra, the rules defined in TTRPG handbooks “participant également de la construction du monde fictionnel” (Caïra 2019). Given the metaphysical importance of these rules, an approach characterized by tugging at loose threads, odd turns of phrase, and uncomfortable framings in the *GURPS* rulebook in turn deconstructs the fiction of RPGs. In order to ground my broader analysis, I choose a case-study: the pre-written adventure “Caravan to Ein-Arris,” which is still included in every purchase of the *GURPS* rulebook to this day (Lambert and Lambert 2004). I use this adventure to extract examples of applications of reaction rolls and skill checks.

When comparing forms of play, we inevitably intersect with questions of *interface*. *GURPS* and *Fallout* both try to emulate the same set of actions on two different mediums. This leads to – materially – wildly different implementations. The hitch is that these implementations share enough vocabulary and grammar for us to string threads from one medium to another. Johanna Drucker’s work on Graphical User Interfaces (GUIs) offers me a methodology to *read interface* and knot these thematic threads (Drucker 2013b). Drucker argues a form of critique whose “task is to understand how [GUIs] organize our relation to complex systems (rather than how they represent them) and ... to understand how an interface works as a boundary space” (Drucker 2013b; 2013a). For my case, this means critically comparing a roleplayed conversation to a dialogue screen [Figure 5] or a GM’s character

management screen to global variables. Thus, at the boundary space between tabletop and computer screen, we are met with even more boundary spaces; when we genuinely place ourselves in relation to the text we are analyzing, fissures are bound to exist everywhere.

Figure 5: A Typical Dialogue Screen in *Fallout*.

As is typical with computer interfaces, I am dealing with an object whose representational and organizational strategies originate in the analogue. As identified by Marie-Laure Ryan, both computer games and table-top roleplaying games share a *mimetic* dimension which “produces a new set of fictional truths” (Ryan 2023). When Ryan writes about “fictional truths,” she is describing the diegetic enactment of roles: mage, knight, vault dweller. However, I am interested in adapting Ryan’s terminology to Drucker’s discussion of interface. In addition to assigning oneself a new name and personality, players engage in mimetic acts of interface.

The dice roll is a canonical example of a mimetic act of interface. Dice rolling has a long history which stretches beyond its usage in role-playing games as a determinate for narrative success or failure. Its origin as a physical act of interface created new fictional truths. The clack of dice against wood is a sound which has been a part of human play for centuries. The most important consequence of this physical materiality is that a player can tell when their game master is rolling dice. This leads to scenarios where the game master is told to lie about what they are rolling for (Lambert and Lambert 2004) or what the result of the roll is – “When all else fails, roll the dice where the players can’t see – and then lie about your roll” (Jackson, Koke, and Smith 2018). The justification for this is always fictional. This kind of *disloyal* relationship to the dice roll is significant because it is *unable to be encoded*. I am primarily interested in these types of unencodable practices.

In *Fallout*, the dice roll is replaced by a silent random number generator. The silence of random number generation intervenes at the Drucker’s “boundary space” of interface. A throw of the dice is replaced by buttons, automatic skill usages, and dialogue [

Figure 6, Figure 7] (Taylor 1997). More complicated and mimetic forms of interface in screen-based RPGs would eventually emerge, but these contemporary interfaces still draw heavily from the practices that *Fallout* canonized. Thus, my attempts at Drucker’s practice of reading interface can be understood as an anthropological exercise: when and how did these structures crystallize into the forms we know today?

Figure 6: The Skill Selection Screen in Fallout

Figure 7: The "Interface Bar" in Fallout

As my presentation traces a genealogy of mimetic and fictional uses of chance, I am curious which aspects of my findings digital humanities as a field can reflect upon. Notions of the unencodable, of the tactile and the silent, and of mimetic interface echo some of the “PROVOCATIONS” posed by *Digital Humanities*: “Is computational work fated to remain in the realm of quantifiable and repeatable phenomena?” (Burdick et al. 2012). These provocations orbit around the notions of *tool* and *implement*. While I traverse the boundary spaces laid out above, I want to keep a kind of ingredient book for a new kind of implementation which turns away from the deterministic and re-enacts role-players’ ludic and disloyal relationship to metrics and repeatability.

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